

Sweat, Fear, Joy, and Amazement: Personal Experience and Mental Journeys of Orthodox Pilgrims to the Holy Land (12th to 15th Century)

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Abstract: This essay analyzes emotionally-charged descriptions of the Holy Land's locations, composed by Byzantine and Slavic pilgrims, from the 12th to the 15th century. The author considers that such episodes were meant to assist the audience in their imaginary journey. By concentrating on curiosities, dangers, beauties of landscape, or physical efforts, the authors created a feeling of presence at the sites, here-and-now. On the other hand, the accounts of pious, bodily performances and the *Erlebnisse* of encounters with the Divine facilitated the audience's access to the spiritual experiences and helped them to conduct the transformative journey mentally.

Key words: descriptions of the Holy Land, pilgrimage, *Erlebnis*, Byzantine writers, Slavic writers

This paper analyzes the descriptions of personal experiences of Byzantine and Slavic pilgrims to the Holy Land, and regards them as rhetorical devices assisting readers in their mental journeys. Consequently, I will survey selected pilgrims' narratives containing the most characteristic individual reflections. I have chosen the timeframe of the

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12th to the 15th century, i.e., between the establishment of the Crusader Kingdoms (1099)² and the fall of Constantinople (1453)³, as during this period, the Byzantine and Slavic travelers, perceived the Holy Land as equally foreign:⁴ they all faced the unknown on the road.

Anthropologists consider pilgrimage as a catalyst triggering deep psychological transformation. Pilgrimage transcends historical, geographical, and social boundaries, and encourages the participants to lose an old identity and to return renewed. By confronting unusual “sequences of sacred objects” and performing “symbolic actions,” a pilgrim experiences changes “from sin to grace, or from sickness to health”⁵. It can be also a quest leading to the life-transforming encounter between the Self and the Other/Divine. Manifested both, temporally and spatially, it establishes a connection between participants and symbolic events of the past⁶. Induced by a spiritual or moral deficiency, a pilgrim, struggling against space, completes a transformative journey to receive an absolution or healing. His trip becomes “the outer manifestation of an inner journey, often referred to as an allegory of the soul’s journey to God”⁷.

When shaped in narratives, the spiritual experiences, even of the same places, vary greatly as the texts of accounts were formed by the modes of description acceptable in one or another cultural context⁸. In Byzantine literature, pilgrimages to the Holy Land were described in a variety of literary genres (*ekphraseis*, *diegeseis*, *vitae*, poems, etc.), but more rarely in form of typical guides (*proskynetaria*)⁹ listing the sacred places. On the contrary, Orthodox Slavs often composed guidebooks (so-called *Hozheniya*¹⁰), *Vitae* (such as the ones of St. Sava of Serbia¹¹ or

2 Lloyd 2002: 35-38.

3 Nicol 1993: 369-393.

4 On Byzantine pilgrims to the Holy Land after the 7th century, see: Griffith 1997; Külzer 1994: 8-13; Talbot 2001; Kuelzer 2017; Pahlitzsch 2018.

5 Turner 1974: 197.

6 Morinis 1992; Osterrieth 1989.

7 Gothóni 1993: 112.

8 For effect of pilgrimage accounts on audiences, see: Frank 2000.

9 Külzer 1994: 82-95; Frank 2000: 79-101; Talbot 2001; Aerts 2003: 169-171; Messis 2011: 149-160.

10 Angelov 1969; Prokof'jev 1984: 10-15; Gyurova, Danova 1985.

11 Domentijan 2001: 280-306; 346-396; Marković 2009. For other Serbian Lives mentioning pilgrims to Jerusalem, see: Jovanović 2007: 94-98, 103, 104.

St. Euphrosyne of Polotsk¹²), and diplomatic reports about Palestine and Sinai.

The texts' functional purpose as well as their intended audience can explain this difference¹³. Artistically refined accounts were composed to please an educated audience and to be performed in the *theatron*¹⁴. The instructive soul-saving writings and guides were intended for a profane or monastic pious gathering, wishing to receive spiritual experience; the inclusion of a pilgrimage in a saint's life had to convince the listeners of the personage's devotion; and, finally, the reports were presented to political elites and officials.

The majority of the Orthodox descriptions of the Holy Land are quite formal, mentioning only the holy places, distances between them, and the related Biblical episodes,¹⁵ thus creating long lists without much of explicit personalization:

... These were holy places within Jerusalem. And these are holy places outside Jerusalem. The Holy Mount of Zion, and in it, there is the site and church of Lithostratos. There Pilate beat Jesus and sent Him to the crucifixion. There is also the home of John the Theologian there...¹⁶

Giving some loose geographical orienteers, the authors of such texts only controlled the order and selection of the places imagined by their audiences and instructed their listeners/readers in the Biblical history. Such textual monotony may be associated with the monastic discourse and could serve to imitate the religious utterances¹⁷; thus, a reading of a pilgrimage description would remind a prayer.

Other pilgrims provided accounts that are more detailed: Russian Abbot Daniel eagerly inspected and very carefully described the religious monuments and curiosities. He provided quite precise information on the preservation, sizes, dimensions, and construction materials as

12 *Zhitiye Evfrosinii* 2003.

13 About Byzantine audiences, see: *Neville* 2019; *Gaul* 2018: 223-225. On Russian audiences, see: *Reshetova* 2006: 29-33, 93-130; *Prokof'jev* 1970: esp. 20-25, 38-40; *Likhachev* 1963.

14 On the Byzantine *theatron*, see: *Cavallo* 2006: 57-66; *Toth* 2007: 437-439, 442-444; *Gaul* 2020.

15 See, for example: *Anonym* 1895; *Anonym* 1890; *Jovanović* 2007: 99-102, 105-109; *Petrova* 1998.

16 *Bdinski Zbornik* 1360: fol. 236v. For further bibliography, see: *Petrova, Angusheva* 1995.

17 *Miller* 1994: esp. 144.

well as on the directions from one site to another. Often, he related the distances in a reader-friendly way, comparing them with arrow shooting or stone throwing:

And from the Resurrection of Christ to the Holy of Holies, the distance is farther than one can shoot [an arrow] twice.

From the place where Christ was baptized to the banks of the Jordan River, the distance is that a man can cast a small stone¹⁸.

This interest in movement, the observation of space in the passage, and the need to distance oneself from changing objects of perception formed a dynamic image of the described territory. Other authors were more eager to establish a landscape of memory, moving through the real space as if through the sacred narrative. Thus, they meticulously instructed their readers into the relations between the holy places and the Gospel passages, as the 14th-century Anonym of St. Sabbas who included extensive quotations from the Scripture right in the body of his text. This way, the itinerary became a framework for the commemoration of Christ's life:

Near this church is the place where they stoned St. Stephen. On the other side is the cave into which Jesus and his disciples entered (just before) the time of suffering, as evangelist John says. 'At that time, Jesus went forth with his disciples over the brook Cedron, where was a garden, into the which he entered, and his disciples (John 18:1); unto a place called Gethsemane, and saith unto the disciples, Sit ye here, while I go and pray yonder...' (Mt. 16:36-38)¹⁹

The preservation of the holy sites and their management, as well as the accounts of miracles contemporary to an author could spark the readers' interest in something distant and exotic and could produce in them a mixture of Christian pity and curiosity. A Russian pilgrim of the 15th century, Zosima, accounted sums he paid for bribes to road-keeping Arabs (15 guard posts between Ramla and Jerusalem) and for the entry to the Holy Sepulcher (7 Venetian forints)²⁰. However, according to Abbot Agrethenios, in the 14th century, the entry price differed for

¹⁸ Khozhdeniye igumena Daniila 1997: 44, 54.

¹⁹ Külzer 1994: 320.

²⁰ Prokof'yev 1984: 309.

Fig. 1. Tomb of the Virgin Mary, Gethsemane, Jerusalem. Founded in the 5th century, rebuilt in the 1130s (photo A. Adashinskaya)

laymen (7 golden coins) and monks/nuns (2 golden coins)²¹. In his *ekphrasis* of the holy places, Perdikas of Ephesus quite often remarked who owned one or another place and how it was administered:

In which there are the church, the cave and the coffin // Of the true Dormition of the holy Virgin Theotokos, // Occupied, as other places, by the unbelievers. Oh, Justice! // The church has uninterrupted lighting and candle-burning // And enjoys all other necessary beauties from those who are there. // Annually, it also receives the oil supply for the lighting, // By the order of the Sultan, of 200 liters, // And, thus, miraculously it brings glory to the Lady of All²².

²¹ Agrethenie 1896: 7.

²² Baseu-Barabas 1997: 170-171.

Fig. 2. The Nativity Grotto, Church of Nativity, Bethlehem. Apse mosaic dated to 12th century (photo A. Adashinskaya)

Perdikas produced in his listeners/readers feelings of fear and amazement simultaneously. Initially, he reported that Muslims occupy this holy place, but shortly after, he narrated about the miracle, namely, that the Sultan of “unbelievers” takes care and financially supports the church. First-hand accounts of miracles not only intrigued the audience, but also entertained and held the listeners’ attention. Deacon Arsenios of Thessaloniki based his entire narrative on the sequence of miracles (*znamenia*) appearing “to this day” at the Lord’s burial, in the Milk Grotto, on Mount Tabor, and other holy locations.²³ However, the predominant narrative strategy for both, Byzantine and Slavic writers, remained the lists of places supplied, sometimes, with short descriptions, measurements, and notes on administration of the holy sites.

Rarely, the authors’ personal voices break through the rigid listing structure and recount some extraordinary events, observations, and details related to personal, emotional, corporal, or spiritual experiences. I assume that such episodes were necessary to provide the models for readers’ spiritual imitation of the journey, their physical and psychical involvement with the venerated places or landscapes, and to convey the sense of emotional engagement, the *Erlebnis*²⁴ of these locations, their existentially important experience and deep personal imprint. Due to strong sentiment of such events for the pilgrim-writers, their descriptions were aimed at transmitting this experience and at influencing the audience²⁵. John Phokas (Doukas²⁶) narrated about such transformative event in his description of the Bethlehem cave. Before recounting the mosaics and marbles ornaments of the cave in details, the 12th-century pilgrim reproduced the moment of joy, fullness with divine love, and a vision of divinity at the point of encounter with the sacred:

... and all creation beheld God in the flesh, and the whole world was made new, and I, mortal as I am, am made rich in the divinity of my God and Creator, who took my poverty upon Himself... I leap for joy as I write, and am altogether in the mind appear in the holy cave, I see the cloth on which the Lord was born, the laying of the new-born

23 *Adrianova* 1913: 195-215; *Gyurova, Danova* 1985: 339-341 (esp. p. 340), 427-434.

24 On M. Heidegger’s and N. Hartmann’s ideas of *Erlebnis* as an experience of event through emotional involvement: *Davey* 2016.

25 H. Hunger noted that the *Erlebnis* was often used in the Ekphraseis conveying an experience through literary impact: *Hunger* 1978: Vol. 1, 182.

26 On the identification of John Doukas, see: *Messis* 2011.

baby in the manger, and I am thrilled by the thought of the Saviour's love for me, and His extreme poverty, through which He has made me worthy of the Kingdom of Heaven. Yet I envision the cave as a palace, and the King sitting upon the Virgin's bosom as upon a throne, and I see the choirs of angels encircling the cave, and the Magi bringing gifts to the King. I am filled with all manner of joy, and I rejoice thinking what grace I have been deemed be worthy to receive²⁷.

However, this experience was not simply a remembrance of past events, but a condition which could be revived in the moment of writing and, possibly, reading/performing. The author projected the *Erlebnis* of his pilgrimage to the point of the *ekphrasis* writing, "I leap for joy as I write," he said. This way, he pointed on the transformative experience whose effects last even after the physical encounter already had taken place.

Both, Byzantine and Slavic authors, interspersed their narratives with positive and negative daily events. Among the most common personal topics are the hardships of ways (heat, absence of water, mountain roads), natural and human-made dangers (wild beasts, bandits), amazement (of natural beauties, fertility of lands, and ancient buildings), and joy associated with the encounter with the divinity. All the inconveniences become a part of the authors' transformative experiences as well as that of the readers/listeners. For example, Daniel of Ephesos accounted for "wasteness of the way and extreme aridity" of the desert, "almost deprived of people, animals, birds, and waters," on his way to Sinai and "the cloudy waters", "the strong current and the thick bank vegetation" of Jordan river²⁸.

Similarly, the hardships of the way may witness for spiritual and physical endurance, necessary to reach the desired goal. The way to a sacred location may be perceived as an achievement resulted from the invested efforts, both, literally and metaphorically. According to Daniel the Abbot, the road to the place of Transfiguration was tiresome and hard:

The mountain is all rock and to climb it over the rock is very difficult and tedious; you have to climb in zigzags and the way is very hard.

²⁷ Ioannos Phokas 1889: 25.

²⁸ Daniel of Ephesos 1884: 3, 8.

*If you climbed briskly from the third to the ninth hour, you would scarcely be able to reach the top of this holy mountain*²⁹.

The dangers of foreign countries could simultaneously entertain and scare the audience. They brought an element of suspense and drove the narrative, attracting attention. Some authors³⁰ encountered wild animals (lions, boars) in the reeds of Jordan River, others³¹ were aggressed by Arabs. Deacon Zosima pointed out to his visit to the holy places “beyond Jerusalem” which were rarely seen due to “the angry Arabs who beat [pilgrims] mercilessly.” He warned the audience that he “endured wounds from the embittered Arabs,” remembering about the tortures of the apostles and martyrs in the course of his own sufferings. Later in the account, he returned to the episode with the Arabs and reported it in more details:

*We went near the Dead Sea, and the evil Arabs attacked us and inflicted severe wounds on me, left me half-dead, and, afterwards, they retreated. I was weak and could hardly reach the Saba monastery in the Valley of Josaphat. Here, I stayed for eight days, and the holy elders provided for me good rest*³².

An experience of landscape of the Holy Land could produce in audience a sense of presence on the described sites with the help of imagination. Abbot Agrethenie recounted the steep ascent to the Mount of Olives and a stunning sight of the holy city and its shrines viewed from the summit³³. Through positioning in space, Daniel the Abbot created an impression of a great and intimidating landscape of Mar Sabba:

The Lavra of St. Saba was established by God in a marvelous and indescribable way: there was a river bed, fearful and very deep and dry and with high walls and, to these walls, cells are attached and held there by God in a marvelous and fearful manner. On the cliffs on both sides of this terrible ravine stand cells fixed to the rocks like

29 Khozhdeniye igumena Daniila 1997: 98.

30 Khozhdeniye igumena Daniila 1997: 54, 90; Prokof'yev 1984: 311.

31 Daniel of Ephesos 1884: 23.

32 Prokof'yev 1984: 306-307, 311.

33 Agrethenie 1896: 11.

Fig. 3. Monastery complex of St. Sabbas the Sanctified (Mar Saba), Palestine, founded in 483 (photo A. Adashinskaya)

*stars in the sky... it is a waterless place in rocky mountains and the whole of that wilderness is dry and waterless*³⁴.

Thus, the author accentuated the natural magnificence of the fearful and marvelous place, alluding to the spiritual power of the monastic community. Using such expressions as “high walls” or “stars in the sky,” Daniel positioned himself as well as the audience in the depth of the gorge looking upwards to the canyon walls and the skies.

Some authors compared the holy landscape with the environmental elements, known to the audience, thus helping them imagine the foreign terrain through the experiences of familiar places. John Phokas saw a similarity between the mountains surrounding the Dead Sea and the peaks, situated near the lake of Ohrid³⁵; Jordan reminded the river Snov’ to Abbot Daniel³⁶, whereas the topography of the lands between

³⁴ Khozhdeniye igumena Daniila 1997: 60.

³⁵ Ioannos Phokas 1889: 19.

³⁶ Khozhdeniye igumena Daniila 1997: 54.

Jordan and Jerusalem could be envisioned as the landscape of Velbužd region by the followers of Constantine of Kostenc' narrative³⁷.

Often, pilgrims mentioned their corporal actions (bowing, kissing, or prostrating) at a holy site, which enabled the readers to execute the acts of veneration mentally. Thus, Andrew Libadenos revered Jerusalem at the very entrance: "we saw all the events of Christ's saving suffering at once; we immediately got off the cars and fell to the ground, praying to the Lord"³⁸. Abbot Agrethenios alluded to the space-induced humble moves of the pilgrims' bodies, when he noted that the entrance to Christ's Tomb is "breast-high and one needs to bow entering"³⁹. One even may assume that the pilgrims' corporal performance was similar to that of St. Sava, as Domentijan narrated it:

... he, with great humility, bowed his knees (knees of heart, of soul and the carnal ones) and shed two streams of pure and warm tears profusely and kissed the life-giving Tomb of his Lord, Christ the benefactor, with his godly [physical] lips and the lips of his heart and soul, sweetly looking at his Beloved one as if He were there⁴⁰.

Such intense veneration, including the prostration and weeping was mirrored in St. Sava's mental actions and prayers as he tried to "bring the holy torments into the depths of his heart" and to embrace the passions of Christ and to imitate the Lord in course of "this transient life." So, the difficult movements and bodily positions worked as reminders about the sufferings of the Lord.

Andrew Libadenos⁴¹ experienced similar transformative events in the Resurrection church. As a climax of his autobiographic story, he "spent a whole night and day inside." He and his fellows, experiencing joy and amazement, "suddenly all tuned the festive hymn to God in honor of His resurrection." After participating in the Liturgy, Andrew's group visited the Lord's burial, where they were overwhelmed by emotions (a mixture of sadness and joy), performed binding and cried:

³⁷ Petrova 1998: 265-266, 269.

³⁸ Andreios Libadenos 1975: 47.

³⁹ Agrethenie 1896: 3-4.

⁴⁰ Domentijan 2001: 282.

⁴¹ Angold 1999: 57; Hinterberger 1999: 290-295.

Here we have cleaned the heads and foreheads, faces and eyes, shed hot tears and come to peace with God, and our eyes shined from within; we prostrate ourselves on the life-giving, all-clean grave and kissed it, and we were filled with pain and joy⁴².

These accounts of *Erlebnis* in the pilgrimages of the late Byzantine and Slavic authors hint about the purposes of these texts: to enable the audience to perform the pilgrimage through the empathic engagement with the descriptions and the faculty of imagination. Daniel of Ephesus set his task as “to provide through the writings” the images of the holy places of Jerusalem for pious readers “as much as they could imagine in their minds”⁴³.

In the same spirit, John Doukas compared sharing the experience through the writings with sharing tasty food in the spirit of “brotherly love”. He likened the travelers who do not share memories of Palestine with the gluttons who eat alone. He thought that the narration was a medium facilitating the access to the immediate experience of the holy places:

It is, therefore, my duty, as much as I can, to create a kind of an outline on a drawing board with the words and to narrate the things we saw immediately through the medium of writings to the pious people, who have never seen the holy places with their own eyes⁴⁴.

Daniel the Abbot equated the physical travelling with the *Erlebnis* happening in the reader’s soul: “For if anyone hearing about these holy places should grieve in his soul and in his thoughts for these holy places, he shall receive the same reward from God as those who shall have travelled to the holy places”⁴⁵. Finally, Zosima regarded his account as transferring the Holy Land’s blessing from the visitor to the reader. From his point of view, those who believe without seeing the sacred sites are superior to the pilgrims who got the proof of their faith:

May this description be a communion blessing from God, from the holy Sepulcher and from all holy places, and those who read may re-

42 Andreios Libadenos 1975: 47-48.

43 Daniel of Ephesus 1884: 1.

44 Ioannos Phokas 1889: 1-2.

45 Khozhdeniye igumena Daniila 1997: 26.

*ceive the reward from God equally with those who saw the holy places of Jerusalem. Blessed are those who see and believe, but three times blessed are those who have not seen, but believed*⁴⁶.

Thus, returning to the anthropologists' definition of pilgrimage as a transformative experience, I suggest that for medieval people, not only a physical voyage, but also a mental journey could be equally transformative. Accounts of Byzantine and Medieval Slavic writers facilitated the audience's emotional engagement with the texts and described places. Thus, the act of reading/listening about the holy sites could turn into the co-participation in the veneration of the divine and into a pious experience in itself.

⁴⁶ Prokof'yev 1984: 315.

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Пот, страх, радост и смайване: лично преживяване и духовно пътуване на православните поклонници до Светите земи (XII–XV век)

Анна Адашинская

Настоящата статия анализира разказите на поклонници от Светите земи, написани от византийски и славянски автори от XII до XV в. Авторът представя гледните точки на антрополозите, свещащи поклонничеството като трансформиращо пътуване, и разглежда предположението, че емоционално наситените разкази на поклонници са подпомагали духовните промени у средновековния читател с помощта на въображението. Въпреки че по-голямата част от поклонническите разкази се състоят от списъци на места с библейско значение, някои автори включват в текстовете си ярки детайли и лични изживявания (Erlebnisse) от пътешествията си. Те разказват за случки, опасности по пътя, за красотите на пейзажите и паметниците и радостта от срещата с божественото. Тези епизоди дават възможност на читателите да тръгнат по пътя на поклонниците, ставайки съпричастни на прочетеното.